

Monthly Briefing #1 - September 2025

It is not a Monthly Briefing 😊

It's more than just an update: it's a space to stay inspired, informed and engaged as we work together to build circular value chains and real change on the ground.

In September, we want to highlight...

Forthcoming Circular Economy Law

The European Commission is working on a proposal for a Circular Economy Law to strengthen the economic security and competitiveness of the Union, while promoting more sustainable production, encouraging circular business models and moving towards decarbonisation.

This legislation aims to facilitate the circulation of circular products, secondary raw materials, and waste within the European market. The aim is to increase the availability of high-quality recycled materials and, at the same time, stimulate demand for these resources throughout the EU.

Go ahead and give your opinion in this public consultation:

[Circular Economy Act](#)

CUSCIT'25 Cement Olympics

The CUSCIT'25 Cement Olympics includes a series of activities designed to enhance the technical skills and visionary perspectives of industry participants, while assessing and promoting their knowledge. This event is a golden opportunity to propose and present circular technologies. United Circles partners from the Ankara Hub will be present.

All information here:

[CUSCIT](#)

United Circles Stakeholder Community

Your knowledge, creativity and perspective are essential to United Circles!!

We invite you to join us, contribute your ideas and play an active role in the transition to a circular future.

Stay tuned and subscribe:

[Stakeholders Community](#)

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